

Efficacy of Floradent Mouthwash in Plaque Control and Periodontal Health: A Clinical Study

Dr. Sakshi Raut¹, Dr. Grishmi Niswade², Dr. Kamlesh Singh³, Dr. Anup Pantawane⁴,
Dr. Rutuja Dani⁵

1. PG student, Department of Periodontology, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur
2. Associate Professor, Department of Periodontology, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur
3. Professor, Department of Periodontology, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur
4. PG student, Department of Periodontology, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur
5. PG student, Department of Periodontology, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur

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Abstract:

Introduction: Floradent mouthwash is a scientifically formulated antiseptic rinse designed to minimize dental plaque and support oral hygiene. It exhibits strong antimicrobial and antiplaque properties, helping to reduce gingival inflammation and prevent periodontal disease, while being gentle on oral tissues and suitable for routine use alongside mechanical plaque control.

Objectives: To evaluate and compare the effectiveness of Floradent mouthwash in reducing dental plaque and gingival inflammation against chlorhexidine.

Methodology: Thirty systemically healthy adults were randomly assigned into test (Floradent mouthwash) and control (Chlorhexidine mouthwash) groups. Subjects rinsed with 10 ml of the assigned mouthwash twice daily after toothbrushing for 28 days. Clinical assessments included Plaque Index, Gingival Index and Gingival bleeding index at baseline, 7, 14 and 21 days.

Results: Both Floradent and Chlorhexidine groups demonstrated significant reductions in plaque accumulation and gingival inflammation over the 4-week period. The clinical efficacy of Floradent was comparable to Chlorhexidine, with no reported adverse effects.

Conclusion: Floradent mouthwash is an effective and safe antiplaque and antiseptic agent, offering similar clinical benefits as Chlorhexidine while being well-tolerated, making it suitable for routine use in periodontal health maintenance.

Keywords – Gingivitis, Herbal mouthwash, Plaque.

INTRODUCTION –

Gingivitis results from substances produced by microbial plaque that accumulates at or near the gingival sulcus.¹ Other local or systemic factors primarily contribute by promoting plaque buildup or retention, or by increasing the vulnerability of gingival tissues to microbial invasion.¹ Dental plaque is a key factor in the initiation and development of gingival inflammation. Histological examination allows characterization of the different stages of gingivitis before the lesion potentially advances to periodontitis. Clinically, gingivitis is readily identifiable.² Mechanical plaque control methods can effectively maintain an adequate level of oral hygiene however, their ability to reduce inflammation and thorough plaque removal is often limited.³ Consequently, there is considerable interest in the use of antimicrobial agents.⁴ Using chlorhexidine mouthwash daily effectively prevented the formation of plaque and gingivitis however it is always backed up by side effects. Advancements in alternative medicine research have resulted in the development of numerous mouthwashes and toothpastes formulated with plant-based extracts.⁵ Currently, there is a growing trend in the utilization of herbal products within the field of dentistry. The aim of this clinical study is to verify the efficacy of herbal mouthwash containing Citrus sinensis, Eugenia jambolana, Mentha piperita, Ptychotis ajowan on reduction of plaque and gingivitis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patients for this study were recruited from the Outpatient Department of Periodontics. The study employed a simple randomized design and included a total of 30 participants. Patients were randomly divided into two groups after obtaining informed consent from all

participants. Group A consisted of individuals who underwent scaling followed by the use of Floradent herbal mouthwash, while Group B included patients who received scaling followed by the use of chlorhexidine mouthwash.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- 1) Age- 20-45 years, males and females
- 2) Systemically Healthy Patients.
- 3) Patients diagnosed with mild to moderate gingivitis.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- 1) Individuals who had taken antibiotics or other medications within the past three months.
- 2) Pregnant or breastfeeding women.
- 3) Patients with any systemic or medical conditions.
- 4) Smokers
- 5) Patients diagnosed with chronic/aggressive periodontitis
- 6) Patients who had not undergone any form of periodontal treatment within the previous six months.

METHODOLOGY

The material used in this study was the herbal mouthwash, Floradent. Each millilitre of Floradent mouthwash contains 10% orange peel extract (*Citrus sinensis*), 10% jamun seed extract (*Eugenia jambolana*), 0.2% pudina satva from mint leaves (*Mentha piperita*), and 0.1% ajowan satva derived from ajwain seeds (*Ptychotis ajowan*)

CLINICAL PARAMETERS

Each patient was evaluated based on the following clinical parameters:

- Plaque Index (Silness and Løe, 1964)
- Gingival Index (Løe and Silness, 1963)
- Gingival bleeding index (Ainamo and Bay, 1975)

After documenting the clinical parameters of the selected participants, thorough scaling was performed for both Group A and Group B using ultrasonic scalers. The primary investigator recorded all clinical parameters, while the co-investigator conducted the treatment procedures. Clinical evaluations were performed at baseline, 7th, 14th and on the 21st day.

USAGE OF MOUTHWASH

After the principal investigator recorded the clinical parameters, participants in both Group A and Group B were advised to rinse with 15 ml of the herbal mouthwash twice daily for 30 seconds once after breakfast and once after dinner. Each participant was instructed to swish and expectorate the rinse after toothbrushing. This standardized regimen was implemented to minimize potential bias associated with variations in brushing habits. Mouthrinses offer an efficient and convenient means of delivering antimicrobial agents, aiding in the removal of food debris and the reduction of bacterial accumulation within the oral cavity, thereby preventing plaque accumulation. Standard oral hygiene instructions were provided to all participants.

RESULTS

The findings revealed a significant decrease in plaque index, gingival index in both Group A and Group B after scaling, as illustrated in Table 2 (Plaque Index), Table 3 (Gingival Index), Table 4 (Gingival Bleeding Index).

Table 1: Intra-examiner variability assessment

COMPONENT	Group A	Group B
Plaque index	0.40	0.71
Gingival index	0.64	0.79

Table 2: Comparison of plaque index scores within the group before and after treatment

Plaque index	Before	After	Mean Difference
Group A	1.688±0.37	1.132±0.35	0.556 ±0.32
Group B	1.641±0.417	0.62 ±0.216	1.021 ±0.355

Table 3: Intra group comparison of gingival index scores before and after treatment

Gingival index	Before	After	Mean difference
Group A	1.790 ±0.343	0.892±0.311	0.898 ±0.408
Group B	1.81±0.28	0.720±0.20	1.09 ±0.29

Table 4: Intra group comparison of gingival bleeding index scores before and after treatment

Gingival Bleeding index	Before	After	Mean difference
Group A	80.857±11.596	36.597±16.562	44.259 ± 0.134
Group B	82.305±11.478	34.594±14.542	61.503 ±0.111

Table 5: Inter group comparison of plaque index , gingival index and gingival bleeding index.

	Group A	Group B	Mean difference
Plaque index	1.132±0.35	0.62 ±0.216	0.512 ± 0.134
Gingival index	0.892±0.311	0.720±0.20	0.172 ±0.111
Gingival Bleeding index	36.597±16.562	34.594±14.542	2.003±2.022

Figure 1: Pre-operative photo at '0' day of Group A

Figure 2: Post-operative photo at '21st' day of Group A

Figure 1: Pre-operative photo at '0' day of Group B

Figure 2: Post-operative photo at '21st' day of Group B

DISCUSSION-

Dental plaque is a structured biofilm composed of numerous microorganisms that adhere to the tooth surface; hence, effective plaque control is essential for maintaining optimal oral hygiene.⁶ Plant-based or herbal formulations have long been utilized in dentistry for their ability to combat microbial growth, alleviate inflammation, calm irritation, and provide pain relief.⁷ The work done by Loe et al (1965)⁸ established that the buildup of bacterial plaque directly leads to gingival inflammation, and that systematic removal and management of this plaque can reverse these lesions in humans. This provided clear evidence supporting plaque as the primary microbial cause of gingivitis, as further discussed by Page et al(1986).⁹ Sinha R et al. (2024)¹⁰ evaluated 60 patients with chronic gingivitis and found that both chlorhexidine and herbal mouthwash groups showed comparable effectiveness in reducing plaque accumulation and gingival inflammation. Safiaghdam H et al (2018)¹¹ concluded that herbal products like mouth rinses and gels effectively reduce gingival inflammation, inhibit plaque, and improve oral hygiene. Pomegranate, aloe, green tea, and miswak show the

strongest evidence for managing gingivitis. Khobragade VR et al (2020)¹² evaluated 30 patients both herbal and chlorhexidine mouthwashes reduced clinical and microbial parameters, with chlorhexidine showing superior results. Oak A et al(2023)¹³ concluded that herbal mouthwashes are a promising alternative and are effective in maintaining oral hygiene. Ardakani MT et al (2022)¹⁴ concluded that the herbal mouthwash improved periodontal health in plaque-induced gingivitis after two weeks. Its effects on probing pocket depth, bleeding on probing, plaque index and gingival index were comparable to 0.2% chlorhexidine mouthwash. Kumar M et al(2024)¹⁵ evaluated that Blue®m group showed a significant reduction in plaque index compared to chlorhexidine, indicating superior antiplaque efficacy. Floradent mouthwash combines orange peel, jamun seed, pudina, and ajowan extracts that offer antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant benefits. Together, they help reduce plaque, control gingival inflammation, and maintain oral freshness whereas Chlorhexidine, introduced in the 1950s, remains one of the most potent antiplaque agents used in dentistry.¹⁶ Its prolonged use, however, is restricted due to its unpleasant taste and tendency to cause brown staining on the teeth.¹⁷

CONCLUSION

Floradent mouthwash effectively reduces dental plaque and gingival inflammation, showing clinical results comparable to chlorhexidine. It is well-tolerated with no reported adverse effects, making it a safe alternative for routine oral hygiene. Its antimicrobial and antiplaque properties support periodontal health, offering a practical option for daily use alongside mechanical plaque control. Additionally, Floradent is a cost-effective formulation, providing an economical choice for maintaining long-term oral health.

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